

DESIGN OF SINGLE-STAGE BUCK BOOST CONVERTER FOR INVERTER APPLICATIONS

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Abstract—In conventional inverters, implementation of a transformer greatly enhances the Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) which is counted to have a negative impact on the inverter output. In order to overcome this limitation, transformer can be replaced by buck and boost converters thereby making a transformer-less inverter which will greatly reduce the THD and enhance the efficiency. In this paper, the design of a single stage buck and boost converters has been presented for photovoltaic inverter applications. The proposed design employs a single-stage switch mode buck converter and a single-stage switch mode boost converter. The converters are so designed that the boost converter provides an output voltage of 312V DC from 24V source while the buck converter provides an output voltage of 7.07V pulsated DC from 312V AC grid. The designed buck and boost converters are then employed to run a single-phase full bridge inverter. The circuit is simulated using the PSIM software. The simulation results show that the designed buck and boost converters can be used to replace transformers from conventional inverter circuit to make low-THD, highly efficient and cost effective transformer-less inverter-topology

IndexTerms—PSIM, Buck, Boost, Buck Boost, Single Phase grid tie Inverter

I. INTRODUCTION

In photovoltaic (PV) system there needs to be a conversion of the solar energy into electrical one through PV arrays using inverter circuit. In conventional inverters, step-up transformers (forward, push-pull, or fly back type) are used to convert unregulated voltage of the PV cells into regulated voltage for the inverter input [1-3]. The main drawback of using a transformer is that it is heavy, bulky, and expensive and has high THD. In order to overcome these limitations, this article proposes to employ a single-stage boost converter in order to make the transformer-less inverter [4-8]. The boost converter is so designed that it provides an output of 312V DC, which is the inverter input.

Moreover, to make a grid-tie inverter, the inverter's phase, frequency and amplitude will have to be the same as that of the grid parameters. To fulfill these grid synchronization conditions, the voltage sample from the grid is taken to produce the gate pulses for switching the inverter's MOSFETs by decreasing the grid voltage to 5V RMS (7.07V AC) using a step-down transformer. Another important point is that the inverter switching is controlled by using microcontroller and its limit cannot be exceeded beyond 5V DC (7.07V AC). In order to attain these features and avail the inverter with advantages of being cost effective, compact and to have dilated THD, in this paper, a single-stage buck converter is recommended to replace the step-down transformer. The buck converter is so designed that it provides an output of 7.07V AC or 5V RMS, which has an output in the shape of an envelope. This envelope is compared with a high frequency triangular wave to produce sinusoidal pulse width modulated (SPWM) signals which are used as the gate signals of the inverter. The buck frequency matches with the grid frequency since the input of buck converter is taken from the grid. The inverter's phase is matched with the grid by applying a zero crossing phase detector with SPWM signal. The inverter's parameters are designed mathematically, and the designed inverter is simulated via PSIM software to verify the inverter's output performances.

II. CONVERTER DESIGN AND RESULTS

Design of Boost Converter

Duty cycle

Duty cycle of the boost converter is calculated considering efficiency of the converter is 95%; the efficiency is added to the duty cycle calculation because this calculation gives a more reasonable duty cycle than just the equation without the efficiency factor.

$$D = 1 - \frac{V_{in}}{V_{out}} \times \eta$$

Inductor Selection

In conventional process the inductor value is chosen from the recommended data sheets. Since no inductor value is given for such a large scale voltage conversion 24V DC to 312V DC. Hence to obtain a good estimated inductor value, the following equation is used which is generated by solving Equation

$$L_{boost} = \frac{V_{in}(V_{out} - V_{in})}{\Delta I \times F_s \times V_{out}}$$